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A Flow Cytometry Study of the non-Fickian Diffusion of Small Charged Molecules in Poly(diallyl dimethyl ammonium chloride) / Poly (styrene sodium sulfonate) Multilayers: Impact of Layer Number, Top Layer and Concentration of Diffusing Molecules

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3 **ABSTRACT:** The diffusion of Sodium dithionite ($S_2O_4^{2-}$) through polyelectrolytes
4 multilayers of poly(diallyl dimethyl ammonium chloride) (PDADMAC)/ poly(styrene
5 sodium sulfonate)(PSS) assembled on colloidal particles with the layer by layer technique is
6 studied by means of flow cytometry and a quenching assay. Fluorescence is provided by a
7 layer of (7-nitrobenz-2-oxa-1,3-diazol-4yl) amino) hexanoate (NBD) labelled poly(allyl
8 amine hydrochloride) assembled below the PDADMAC/PSS multilayer. NBD is quenched
9 by a redox reaction with $S_2O_4^{2-}$. NBD quenching is fast at short times but strongly retarded
10 at longer times. Quenching is faster for PDADMAC as top layer and for increasing
11 concentrations of $S_2O_4^{2-}$. The quenching kinetics of NBD is described with a model assuming
12 a non-Fickian diffusion of $S_2O_4^{2-}$, with diffusion coefficients that depend on time with an
13 inverse power law. Diffusion coefficients show little dependence on the number of layers but
14 are highly dependent on the concentration of $S_2O_4^{2-}$. Increasing the concentration of $S_2O_4^{2-}$
15 over 10 mol/m^3 results in a decrease of diffusion coefficient, more evident at longer times.
16 The non-Fickian behavior for $S_2O_4^{2-}$ diffusion is explained on the basis of the trapping of
17 dithionite in the multilayers.
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INTRODUCTION

The sequential assembly of oppositely charged polyelectrolytes based on electrostatic interactions, the so called layer by layer technique (LbL), offers a simple and versatile tool for the hierarchical engineering surfaces without relying on covalent chemistry¹⁻⁵.

Polyelectrolyte multilayers (PEMs) assembled by the LbL technique have found many potential applications as protective coatings, for device fabrication, optics, energy applications, and in pharma and medicine⁶. PEMs have indeed large perspectives in control delivery. A large number of works in previous years have dealt with the use of PEMs for capsule fabrication, using sacrificial templates, as a mean to encapsulate drugs and therapeutics inside the capsule inner volume^{7,8}. Other promising strategies are based on the encapsulation of large therapeutics being assembled in between polyelectrolyte layers in PEMs in onion ring like structures⁹.

For the use of PEMs in encapsulation and drug delivery is important to understand how drugs permeate through the polyelectrolyte multilayers as it is fundamental to control the release of encapsulated molecules for therapeutic applications¹⁰⁻¹². Diffusion in PEMs is also relevant for the use of PEMs as filtration membranes¹³⁻¹⁵. Besides, studying the diffusion of molecules through multilayers is an issue of fundamental physical interest. PEMs are an example of layered films with alternating layers of opposite charges that in the case of the diffusion of charged molecules can result in consecutive repulsive and attractive interactions along the film¹⁶.

Recently, we have shown a novel methodology for measuring diffusion of small molecules in PEMs¹⁷. This methodology is based on the use of colloidal particles, a quenching assay, and flow cytometry¹⁸. Poly (allyl amine hydrochloride) (PAH) and poly(styrene sodium)

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3 (PSS) PEMs are assembled on top of colloidal particles. Selected PAH layers are covalently
4 labelled with the fluorescent dye (7-nitrobenz-2-oxa-1,3-diazol-4yl)amino hexanoate
5 (NBD)^{17,19}. Sodium dithionite ($S_2O_4^{2-}$) is studied as diffusing small molecule. $S_2O_4^{2-}$
6 quenches the fluorescence of NBD. The quenching takes place by chemical reduction of the
7 7-aminobenzene into a 7-nitrobenzene group, which leads to a complete and irreversible loss
8 of fluorescence. Flow cytometry allows to measure the fluorescence of individual particles
9 in a colloidal dispersion. The fluorescence can be recorded for a large number of particles in
10 a dispersion, each carrying a labelled PEM, with the advantage of a large statistics in one
11 single measurement. From the variations in the fluorescence intensity with time for the
12 particle population a fluorescence decay curve is obtained, which is fitted with an appropriate
13 model obtaining the diffusion coefficient of the dithionite in the layers. Surprisingly, we
14 observed for the PAH/PSS multilayers a very slow diffusion for $S_2O_4^{2-}$ that cannot be
15 modelled following a traditional Fickian law. Data can be modelled only assuming that the
16 diffusion coefficient decreases with the diffusing time with a power law.

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19 Since experiments were all performed with PAH/PSS multilayers we decided to extend our
20 work to multilayers with different chemistry, first to prove the applicability of the flow
21 cytometry quenching assay to other multilayers, and second to determine if the slow diffusion
22 and time dependence of the diffusion coefficient observed, which was interpreted as a result
23 of the trapping of dithionite in positively charged layers, is a more general phenomena and
24 not restricted to PAH/PSS film¹⁷.

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27 Therefore, we adapted the quenching assay for measuring the diffusion of dithionite
28 through poly(diallyl dimethyl ammonium chloride) (PDADMAC)/PSS multilayers
29 (Scheme 1). PDADMAC was chosen as polycation for several reasons. First,
30 PDADMAC/PSS films are a very well-studied multilayer, with quite different characteristics

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3 from PAH/PSS multilayers. PDADMAC/PSS show a supralinear growth while PAH/PSS
4 grow linearly^{20,21}. Differently from PAH, PDADMAC is a polycation bearing quaternary
5 amines, and as such amines in PDADMAC cannot be labelled like in PAH²². This lead us to
6 find a more general approach to measure fluorescence in PEMs regardless of the fact that
7 the polymers in the films can be labelled or not. Then, we will adapt the architecture of the
8 film to include a labelled layer of PAH^{NBD}. We will show that the diffusion of small
9 molecules through PDADMAC/PSS films can be studied with flow cytometry and the
10 quenching assay when we assembly first a PAH/PSS film on colloids with a top layer of
11 PAH^{NBD}.

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24 On top of the PAH^{NBD} layer we will assembly a multilayer of PDADMAC and PSS of up
25 to 5 polyelectrolyte layers. Quenching experiments will be performed with colloids coated
26 with 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 layers of polyelectrolytes on top of PAH^{NBD}. For each sample the
27 concentration of dithionite quenchers from 1 to 100 mol/m³ (1 mM to 100 mM). We observe
28 that diffusion of dithionite is affected by the sign of the top layer in the PEM and strongly
29 depended on dithionite concentration. Diffusion of dithionite can be considered as non-
30 Fickian, displaying an inverse dependence of the diffusion coefficient on time with an
31 inverse power law. We will show that the non-Fickian behavior and the dependence of the
32 diffusion coefficient with time will decrease as the concentration of dithionite increases,
33 which can be explained by the architecture of polyelectrolyte multilayers and the interaction
34 of dithionite with polyelectrolytes.

51 MATERIALS

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53 Silica particles (diam: 3.03 ± 0.17 μm) were purchased from microParticles GmbH (Berlin,
54 Germany). PAH (MW 70 000 Da), PSS (MW 70 000 Da), PDADMAC (MW 200 000 – 350
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3 000 Da) and Sephadex G-25 chromatography gel were obtained from Sigma (Deisenhofen,
4 Germany). Succinimidyl 6-(N(7-nitrobenz-2-oxa-1,3-diazol-4yl)amino) hexanoate (S-NBD)
5 was purchased from Molecular Probes (Eugene, Oregon). Molecular porous membrane
6 tubing (MWCO: 12 000 - 14 000 Da) was purchased from Spectrum Laboratories, Inc.
7 (California). All other chemicals were obtained from Fluka (Neu-Ulm, Germany).

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14 **Labelling of PAH.** For the labelling of PAH with S-NBD the dye was dissolved in
15 carbonate buffer, containing 10% DMF (v/v), before being added in a dropwise fashion to
16 PAH dissolved a in 0.1 M carbonate buffer at pH 8.5. This mixture was then allowed to react
17 for 48 h. Following incubation, the polymer solution was passed through a Sephadex Gel
18 chromatography column to separate NBD-labelled PAH and free dye. The remaining buffer
19 was removed by dialysis. The labelled and purified polyelectrolytes were lyophilized and
20 stored at 4 °C for future use. The labelling degree, the ratio of dye molecules attached to one
21 polyelectrolyte molecule, was determined by comparing the absorbance of the solution of
22 lyophilized labelled PAH in 0.5 M NaCl, with the absorbance of a calibration series of the
23 dye. UV-vis measurements were performed on a Cary 50 spectrometer (Varian Instruments)
24 using the molar extinction coefficient $\epsilon_{484} = 41\,200\text{ M}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for NBD. Furthermore, labelled
25 PAH will be referred to as PAH^{NBD}.

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42 **Particle Coating.** Coating of silica particles with PEMs was performed as follows: at first
43 the bulk solution of particles (500 μL , 5 wt%, and approximate surface area 0.025 m^2) was
44 centrifuged, and the supernatant was discarded. Particles were then dispersed again in 200
45 μL of 0.5 M NaCl. This suspension was pipetted into a 1 mg/mL solution of PAH in 0.5 M
46 NaCl and incubated under constant stirring for 10 min. Next, the colloids were centrifuged
47 at 650 g for 2 min and washed with 0.1 M NaCl. The washing procedure was repeated 3 times
48 to remove excess of polyelectrolyte. Then, a 1 mg/mL solution of PSS in 0.5 M NaCl was
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3 added to form the next polyelectrolyte layer. After PSS adsorption, particles were washed in
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5 distilled water. This procedure of centrifugation, washing, and alternate adsorption of
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7 oppositely charged polyelectrolytes were repeated till the assembly 4 polyelectrolyte layers
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9 ([PAH-PSS]₂) on top of the silica. At this point a layer of PAH^{NBD} was adsorbed. Then, one
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11 further PSS layer was deposited. Afterwards, following the same procedure as for [PAH-
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13 PSS]₂ PDADMAC/PSS layers were assembled [PDADMAC-PSS]₂. Fluorescence decay data
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15 were obtained after each polyelectrolyte layer assembled beginning from the PAH^{NBD} layer.
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19 **Flow Cytometry.** Flow cytometry measurements were performed with a FACS Calibur
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21 flow cytometer (Becton Dickinson, U.S.A., with an air-cooled argon ion laser, 15-mW, 488-
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23 nm. Time-dependent assays were conducted over 1-3 min with a time resolution of 1 s.
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25 Recording of the fluorescence started 3 s after addition of sodium dithionite. For each
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27 measurement the solution of dithionite was freshly prepared (1 M) in 0.1 M Tris (pH 10.0).
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29 The amount of sodium dithionite was kept to have a molar ratio of dithionite to NBD of 1.6
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31 $\times 10^8$. The geometric mean values of the fluorescence intensity distribution within every
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33 second were calculated. The particle solutions were diluted to a concentration of
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35 approximately 50 counts per second. The geometric mean of 50 consecutive counts was
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37 calculated. The highest and lowest calculated values of these geometric means were taken as
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39 the error limits of the method. Single particles were gated on the basis of their light scattering
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41 to separate them from the aggregates since there is a linear increase of forward scattering
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43 with the size of the aggregates. The data were analysed using WinMDI 2.8 software.
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49 **Fluorescence Spectroscopy.** Fluorescence spectroscopy measurements were performed
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51 using a Fluoromax 2 fluorescence spectrometer (Spec Industries., Inc., U.S.A.). The
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53 excitation wavelength was set at 467 nm for NBD.
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3 **ζ -Potential Measurements.** ζ potentials were measured in water using Brookhaven
4 *ZetaPALS*. Measurements were performed in 10 mM KCl. Each Measurement was repeated
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7 5 times, and afterward the mean value and the standard deviation were calculated.
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10 11 12 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

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15 We have shown in a previous work¹⁷ that the diffusion of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ in PAH/PSS PEMs can be
16 studied via the quenching of the fluorescence emission of NBD covalently bound to PAH
17 and assembled in the PEM. The fluorescence of NBD is quenched by $S_2O_4^{2-}$, the diffusing
18 molecule, which reduces NO_2 groups in NBD to NH_2 while it oxidizes to SO_2^- .
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25 In this current work we have studied the diffusion of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ in PDADMAC/PSS PEMs.
26 PDADMAC cannot be labelled as PAH since all amine groups are quaternary and is not
27 possible to functionalize them covalently. Therefore, we developed the following strategy:
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29 we first assembled a multilayer of PAH/PSS with NBD labelled PAH as last layer. On top
30 of the layer of PAH labelled with NBD PSS and PDADMAC were alternately assembled up
31 to 5 layers. PAH/PSS layers are assembled to ensure that the NBD labelled PAH will cover
32 the surface of the colloids smoothly. The two block PEM with the initial block of PAH/PSS
33 and top layer NBD labelled PAH and a second block of PDADMAC/PSS is sketched in
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45 To follow the assembling of polyelectrolyte layers on silica particles the ζ potentials were
46 measured after each layer was assembled on the particles.
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Figure 1. ζ potential measurements as a function of layer number. Initial layers are formed by PAH and PSS till the 5th layer (PAH^{NBD}), from the 5th layer PDADMAC and PSS are assembled until the 10th layer.

The ζ potential alternates from positive to negative values according with the charge of the polyelectrolyte assembled. PAH or PDADMAC assembly results in a positive potential, +50 mV, while the assembly of PSS brings a negative potential to the particles, around -50 mV. PAH is assembled as polycation until the 5th layer. From the 5th layer till the 10th PDADMAC is assembled.

We can conclude from these experiments that the layer by layer assembly is continuous and that the assembly of PDADMAC on top of PAH/PSS is successful.

Once PEMs are assembled the fluorescence of the silica particles coming from PAH^{NBD} before and after dithionite addition is measured by flow cytometry as sketched in Scheme 1. In the flow cytometer particles are flown one by one in front of laser by hydrodynamic

Scheme 2. Histograms at 3 different times after the dithionite was added (5s, 120s, 300s). Fluorescence decay curve obtained from the histograms at different times after $S_2O_4^{2-}$ addition.

Dot plots from the flow cytometer measurements have been transformed into histograms, where the intensity of fluorescence is placed at the X axis and the number of particles in the Y axis. Only fluorescence from single particles is taken into consideration. Fluorescence events from aggregates have been removed. From each histogram the average fluorescence intensity is calculated and used to build the fluorescence decay curve in scheme 2 together with the time at which the histogram is recorded after $S_2O_4^{2-}$ addition. In the curve it can be appreciated a delay from the first measurement, at time 0, and the first experiments with $S_2O_4^{2-}$. As the measurements are not sequential, the fluorescence intensities at time 0 and 3s after dithionite addition are not connected with each other. The fluorescence intensity

distribution is scaled logarithmically in the respective histograms and dot plots. Finally, the fluorescence decay is normalized with respect to the initial fluorescence values and plotted as relative fluorescence (Figure 2). The fluorescence decay curve shows the time evolution of the average fluorescence for the colloidal dispersion. From the analysis of the fluorescence decay curve we will obtain information on the diffusion of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ in PDADMAC/PSS multilayers¹⁷.

Experiments were performed with different concentrations of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ quencher: 1 mol/m³, 3 mol/m³, 10 mol/m³, 30 mol/m³, 100 mol/m³ (1 mM to 100 mM).

Figure 2. a) Normalized fluorescence as a function of time for $[PAH-PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}-PSS-[PDADMAC-PSS]_2$ at 1 mol/m³, 3 mol/m³, 10 mol/m³, 30 mol/m³, 100 mol/m³ $S_2O_4^{2-}$ concentrations. b) relative fluorescence for PEMs starting with $[PAH-PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}$ till $[PAH-PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}-PSS-[PDADMAC-PSS]_2$, per each layer deposited, and a fixed quencher concentration of 3 mol/m³. Time on the time axis corresponds to 600 s.

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3 In Figure 2 selected fluorescence decay curves are shown. All experimental curves have
4 common characteristic features. Fluorescence decreases over the time after the addition of
5 $S_2O_4^{2-}$. Over short time scales quenching is rapid, while over longer time scales the quenching
6 process is strongly retarded. In Figure 2a the relative fluorescence vs time decay curves for
7 $[PAH-PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}-PSS-$ $[PDADMAC-PSS]_2$ for 1 mol/m³, 3 mol/m³, 10 mol/m³, 30
8 mol/m³, 100 mol/m³ $S_2O_4^{2-}$ are shown. The decay curves show that the fluorescence decreases
9 faster with increasing concentrations of $S_2O_4^{2-}$. At 1 mol/m³ the fluorescence decays to a 90%
10 of the initial fluorescence after 600s while at 100 mol/m³ the decay is to a 70% of the initial
11 fluorescence for the same time.
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24 In Figure 2b the normalized fluorescence decay curves for silica particles with $[PAH-$
25 $PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}$, and the particles with PSS and PDADMAC layers on top are shown for 3
26 mol/m³ Dithionite. The fastest quenching takes place for the silica particles with $[PAH-$
27 $PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}$ as outermost layer (Figure 2b black curve). From the curves it can be inferred
28 that the charge of the top layer has an impact on the quenching kinetics. From Figure 2b it is
29 obvious that the curves are separated into two groups corresponding to fast quenching
30 kinetics in the bottom and relatively slow quenching kinetics in the top. Indeed, PEMs with
31 PSS as top layer show a decrease to an 80% of the original fluorescence after 600s. PEMs
32 with positive top layers show a decrease to up to a 60% of the initial fluorescence for PAH
33 as last layer while for the PEMs with last layer PDADMAC the decrease diminishes up to a
34 65-70% of the initial intensity after 600s. $S_2O_4^{2-}$ is negatively charged and therefore will
35 experience electrostatic repulsion by the sulfonate groups of PSS and will bind to the
36 positively charged - groups of PAH and PDADMAC The faster quenching for positive
37 charged top layers is a consequence of the concentration of the quencher at the boundary of
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3 the film being increased through electrostatic attraction. The same behavior was observed for
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5 the different concentrations of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ studied.
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8 In the current work a crucial point is that only one layer of the PEM is labeled with NBD.
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10 It means that by each layer that is added on the top of $[PAH-PSS]_2-PAH^{NBD}$ PEM the distance
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12 between quencher in bulk and fluorescent label, dithionite and NBD respectively, will be
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14 increased.
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17 Fluorescence decays as a consequence of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ coming into close proximity and binding
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19 to NBD, which will be reduced and will no longer fluoresce. The model that has been
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21 suggested in our previous work¹⁷ to analyze the binding kinetics of the quencher with the
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23 label needs to be modified as here we have a PEM with only one labeled layer instead of
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25 several layers.
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28 For the development of a theoretical model, let us consider the one-dimensional diffusion
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30 of quenchers along the x-axis, which is perpendicular to the interface of the quencher solution
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32 with the polyelectrolyte film.
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35 We place the origin of our coordinate system at the interface and direct x-axis to the
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37 direction of the substrate, on which the film is placed. The following boundary conditions
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39 are assumed:
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42 The concentration of the quenchers is kept constant in the solution, equal to C_Q^{Eq} .
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45 The concentration of quenchers in arbitrary point of polyelectrolyte film depends on the x
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47 coordinate as well as on time t, i.e. we have $C_Q(x,t)$.
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50 There are fixed labels in the polyelectrolyte film in some x_2-x_1 layer, whose initial
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52 concentration is equals to C_{L0} . At an arbitrary point in time the concentration of the label is
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54 equal to $C_L(x,t)$. Initially all labels are intact, hence the fluorescence intensity is at a
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56 maximum. As time progresses quenchers penetrate into the polyelectrolyte film, gradually
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3 filling it, and when a quencher meets a label, a chemical reaction occurs and the label is
4 quenched. The substrate interface is impermeable for quenchers. The binding kinetics of the
5 quencher to the label can be divided into two steps, namely: a diffusion step of the quenchers
6 inside the polyelectrolyte multilayers approaching to labels and, a kinetic step of binding of
7 quenchers with labels, which are in the layer at the thickness x_2-x_1 . As the polyelectrolyte
8 film is filled with the quencher molecules, the fluorescence intensity of the film will decrease.
9 Therefore, the quencher concentration will change with time at an arbitrary point in the
10 polyelectrolyte film not only due to diffusion but, also because it decreases due to the binding
11 with NBD labels.
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24 As it was done in¹⁷ we also assume here that the binding of the quenchers with labels is
25 fast, and the concentration of labels in the polyelectrolyte film is small, so the change in
26 concentration of the quencher in the film occurs only due to its diffusion. Since the labels are
27 fixed, the change in their concentration will occur as a result of their binding with quenchers
28 and subsequent quenching. The slow diffusion kinetics of the quenchers can be explained by
29 the decrease of the diffusion coefficient with time²³. The solution of the corresponding
30 system of partial differential equations is described in details in¹⁷, however one should take
31 into account that the redox reaction of the quencher with label is taking place in some layer
32 inside the film, where the labels are located. This leads to the following modification of the
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$$\frac{\partial c_Q(x,t)}{\partial t} = D(t) \frac{\partial^2 c_Q(x,t)}{\partial x^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_L(x,t)}{\partial t} = -k c_L(x,t) c_Q(x,t) (H(x_1) - H(x_2)) \quad (2)$$

where $D(t)$ - is the diffusion coefficient of the quencher in the polyelectrolyte layer and is represented in the following way $D(t) = D_0 / t^{1-\alpha}$, t is the time, (D_0 и α -parameters), is the binding rate constant of the quencher with the label, $H(x)$ - Heaviside function. It is important to notice that the quenching kinetics is related to the number of collisions between the molecules of quencher and label, i.e. in fact it is proportional to the product of their concentrations. Because of this the equation system (1),(2) becomes nonlinear and can describe the complex process of quencher diffusion and label quenching. By solving this system of equations (1), (2) it is possible to obtain the following final expression for the quenching kinetics of the label in the polyelectrolyte film in case of the layer with x_2-x_1 thickness in which the labels are located is on the substrate:

$$\frac{F(t)}{F(0)} = \int_{\xi_1}^1 \exp \left(-k_0 \left(\frac{t}{t_1} \right)^\alpha - \frac{16}{\pi^3} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \left(\frac{(2n+1)\pi\xi}{2} \right)}{(2n+1)^3} \left(1 - \exp \left(-\frac{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2}{4} \left(\frac{t}{t_1} \right)^\alpha \right) \right) \right) d\xi / \int_{\xi_1}^1 d\xi$$

$$k_0 = 4\pi l^2 R_c c_Q^{Eq}, \quad t_1 = (l^2 \alpha / D_0)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}. \quad (3)$$

where t is time, l - the thickness of the film, R_c - effective reaction radius of the label, $\xi = x / l$ - dimensionless length, ξ_1 - dimensionless distance between layer with label and the substrate. Using the formula (3) the experimental curves of quenching kinetics of the label in case of different variants of location of the label containing layer from the interface of the quencher solution with the polyelectrolyte film and the dependence of the quenching kinetics on quencher's concentration were described. Theoretical curves describing

experimental data are obtained by fitting with the least square method and using the equation (3). The experimental data are fitted by the theoretical curve (3). The accuracy of the fitting to the experimental data is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Experimental data and their fitting in log-log scales, for $[\text{PAH-PSS}]_2\text{-PAH}^{\text{NBD}}\text{-PSS-PDADMAC}$ and 30 mol/m^3 dithionite.

From Figure 3 it can be seen that the theoretical curve obtained by formula (3) describes the experimental results quite well. In the Figure the fitting is shown for $[\text{PAH-PSS}]_2\text{-PAH}^{\text{NBD}}\text{-PSS-PDADMAC}$ and $30 \text{ mol/m}^3 \text{ S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$. As all fitted curves are analogical to this one, they are not shown. D_0 and α parameters were defined by the fitting.

The D_0 and α values obtained for the PEMs studied in presence of 1 mol/m^3 , 3 mol/m^3 , 10 mol/m^3 , 30 mol/m^3 , $100 \text{ mol/m}^3 \text{ S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ are represented in table 1. As it can be seen from the table the range of variation of α is 0.09-0.43 and for D_0 $1.11\text{-}125.83 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$. The order of magnitude of the obtained values is in a good correspondence with the values obtained for D_0 and α by us earlier in case of PAH/PSS PEM multilayers¹⁷.

Table 1. The Calculated Values of D_0 and α in Case of Different Concentration of the Quencher for the Mentioned PEM Systems

PEM system	$C_Q^{Eq} = 1$ mol/m ³	$C_Q^{Eq} = 3$ mol/m ³	$C_Q^{Eq} = 10$ mol/m ³	$C_Q^{Eq} = 30$ mol/m ³	$C_Q^{Eq} = 100$ mol/m ³	parameters
[PAH-PSS] ₂ - PAH ^{NBD}	0.28	0.26	0.22	0.18	0.15	α
	125.83	58.25	15.95	5.37	2.05	$D_0, 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$
[PAH-PSS] ₂ - PAH ^{NBD} - PSS	0.43	0.26	0.22	0.14	0.13	α
	77.6	20.37	8.4	2.38	1.11	$D_0, 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$
[PAH-PSS] ₂ - PAH ^{NBD} - PSS- PDADMAC	0.3	0.18	0.15	0.12	0.091	α
	108.2	48.71	11.47	4.83	2.48	$D_0, 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$
[PAH-PSS] ₂ - PAH ^{NBD} - PSS- PDADMAC-PSS	0.32	0.29	0.13	0.13	0.095	α
	96.88	31.5	13.52	4.35	2.08	$D_0, 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$
[PAH-PSS] ₂ - PAH ^{NBD} - PSS- PDADMAC-PSS- PDADMAC	0.24	0.22	0.13	0.12	0.09	α
	82.11	44.16	8.13	3.71	1.78	$D_0, 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$
[PAH-PSS] ₂ - PAH ^{NBD} - PSS- [PDADMAC-PSS] ₂	0.25	0.19	0.16	0.13	0.09	α
	59.13	31.8	9.68	7.86	4.71	$D_0, 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}^\alpha$

From the results in Table 1 it is obvious that the concentration of the quencher has much more influence on diffusion parameters D_0 and α than the thickness of the layers i.e. increasing the distance between the label and the quencher in bulk. For all layers the D_0 decreases nearly 50 times when the concentration of the quencher increases from 1 mol/m³ to 100 mol/m³. In case of 1 mol/m³, 3 mol/m³, 10 mol/m³ dithionite some variations in the values of D_0 and α passing from layer to layer can be observed.

As diffusion coefficient depends on time the description of quenching kinetics only with D_0 and α is not so accurate, it makes sense to consider the diffusion coefficient's as a function of time. Using the results from Table 1, it is possible to plot the dependence of diffusion

coefficient from time for the curves shown in Figure 2. The curves of $D(t)$ are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The dependence of diffusion coefficient on time for a) $[\text{PAH-PSS}]_2\text{-PAH}^{\text{NBD}}\text{-PSS-}[\text{PDADMAC-PSS}]_2$ at 1 mol/m^3 , 3 mol/m^3 , 10 mol/m^3 , 30 mol/m^3 , 100 mol/m^3 $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ concentrations. (refers to curves in Figure 2a) b) for PEMs starting with $[\text{PAH-PSS}]_2\text{-PAH}^{\text{NBD}}$ till $[\text{PAH-PSS}]_2\text{-PAH}^{\text{NBD}}\text{-PSS-}[\text{PDADMAC-PSS}]_2$, quencher concentration of 3 mol/m^3 (refers to curves in Figure 2b). Time on the time axis corresponds to 600 s.

From Figure 4 it can be seen that characteristic features of non-Fickian diffusion; namely, the fast diffusion over short timescales and slow diffusion over longer timescales are intrinsic for $D(t)$ dependence. The diffusion coefficient shows a different dependence on time if compared with the quenching kinetics in Figure 2. The reason for differences observed between the curves shown in Figures 2 and 4 is actually that the quenching kinetics depends not only on the diffusion coefficient of the quencher, but also on the quencher's concentration at the boundary of polyelectrolyte multilayer and on the thickness of multilayer. The non-

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3 Fickian diffusion observed can be explained by the complexation of the dithionite with
4 positive charges of PDADMAC, which act as trap for the $S_2O_4^{2-}$. Dithionite will face
5 negative and positive charges along the diffusion through the film. Negative charges from
6 PSS result in repulsion. This repulsion is indeed responsible of the lower $S_2O_4^{2-}$ concentration
7 at the interface of the PEM when PSS is the last layer. Because of this concentration decrease
8 at the interface of the PEM the fluorescence decay for PEMs with last layer negative is always
9 less pronounced than for PEMs with top layer positive as we observe in Figure 2. Inside the
10 multilayers we can assume that PSS layers must have a retarding effect preventing $S_2O_4^{2-}$
11 from going through or forcing dithionite to go through regions in the layers where the density
12 of negative charges is lower. However, once the $S_2O_4^{2-}$ goes through the negative layer the
13 repulsive interaction with the PSS molecules will help to confine $S_2O_4^{2-}$ inside the layers.
14 PDADMAC layers on the other hand have the mentioned trapping effect. For PEMs with
15 PDADMAC as last layer there is an increase in the concentration of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ at the interface,
16 favored by the electrostatic attraction between the positive charges of PDADMAC and the
17 negatively charged $S_2O_4^{2-}$, which induces a faster quenching. However, the trapping in the
18 layers must have a retarding effect, as $S_2O_4^{2-}$ complexation with the amines of PDADMAC
19 should prevent its diffusion. The binding of $S_2O_4^{2-}$ to the amines of PDADMAC should
20 restrict additional $S_2O_4^{2-}$ ions from binding to the amines and the trapping effect should be
21 less pronounced as the concentration increases. We must take into consideration that $S_2O_4^{2-}$
22 bound to PDADMAC should have a repulsive interaction for additional $S_2O_4^{2-}$ ions. This
23 repulsion should additionally contribute to a slow quenching. When we look at the curves in
24 Figure 4b and we do not consider the decay curve corresponding to NBD labelled PAH as
25 top layer diffusion coefficients do not change so much for a specific dithionite concentration.
26 Clearly, PDADMAC terminated PEMs show a higher diffusion coefficient both at the fast
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3 and slow diffusion regime than PSS terminated ones. These slight differences in the diffusion
4 coefficients are most likely a consequence of the increased concentration of dithionite for
5 PDADMAC as top layer and the decrease in concentration in the opposite case. Curves in
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10 Figure 4b show quenching experiments at $3 \text{ mol/m}^3 \text{ S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$. In Figure 4a we observe that at
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13 $10 \text{ mol/m}^3 \text{ S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ the diffusion coefficients at longer times become very small, almost 0. At
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15 higher $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ concentration, i.e. 100 mol/m^3 , this issue becomes more evident. Moreover, the
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17 fast diffusion at short times also decreases with increasing $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ concentration. The
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19 saturation of quaternary amines at concentrations higher than $10 \text{ mol/m}^3 \text{ S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ and the
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21 repulsion of diffusing $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ by the dithionite complexed in the layers and the negative
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23 charges of PSS could explain this behavior. The non-Fickian diffusion in the layers is
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25 associated with the trapping of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ by PDADMAC, which is conditioned by the
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27 concentration of dithionite. At higher dithionite concentrations the positive charges of
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29 PDADMAC are saturated with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ preventing further $\text{S}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ions from complexing with
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31 PDADMAC, which results in a decrease of the dependence of the diffusion coefficient with
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40 CONCLUSIONS

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In this work, it is shown that the diffusion of the small molecule dithionite in polyelectrolyte layers of PDADMAC/PSS can be studied via flow cytometry. The methodology shown can be applied for any PEM composition provided that can be assembled on top of a labelled polyelectrolyte layer. The diffusion kinetics of the dithionite in polyelectrolyte multilayer takes place in a non-classical way: the quenching kinetics over short timescales is fast, and over long timescales is slow. The quenching kinetics of the label depends on the sign of the

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3 surface charge of polyelectrolyte film. If the signs of the charge of the quencher and
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5 outermost polyelectrolyte layer are the same then the quenching kinetics proceeds more
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7 slowly, if the charges have opposite signs then the quenching kinetics is faster. For a
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9 theoretical description of the slow quenching kinetics we suppose that the diffusion
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11 coefficient decreases with the time in an inverse power law. Fitting experimental curves of
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13 the quenching kinetics of the labels with theoretical curves allows us to obtain values of
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15 parameters of diffusion coefficient and to characterize quantitatively the transport properties
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17 of polyelectrolyte layers.
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21 We assume that the reason of non-Fickian diffusion is the electrostatic interaction between
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23 the quencher and oppositely charged groups in the polyelectrolyte film acting as a trap for
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25 $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and the repulsion by negative charges. Increasing dithionite concentration results in a
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27 faster quenching of the fluorescence but at the same time the calculated diffusion coefficients
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29 decrease. Over $10 \text{ mol/m}^3 S_2O_4^{2-}$ the values of the diffusion coefficient at long times are very
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31 low, almost 0, which can be interpreted as result of the saturation of the amines in
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33 PDADMAC by $S_2O_4^{2-}$.
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REFERENCES

1. Lvov, Yu.; Ariga, K.; Ichinose, I.; Kunitake, T. Assembly of Multicomponent Protein Films by Means of Electrostatic Layer-by-Layer Adsorption. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1995**, *117*, 6117 – 6123.
2. Donath, E.; Sukhorukov, G. B.; Caruso, F.; Davis, S. A.; Möhwald H. Novel Hollow Polymer Shells by Colloid-Templated Assembly of Polyelectrolytes. *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **1998**, *37*, 2201 – 2205.
3. Donath, E.; Moya, S.; Neu, B.; Sukhorukov, G. B.; Georgieva, R.; Voigt, A.; Baumler, H.; Kiesewetter, H.; Möhwald, H. Hollow Polymer Shells from Biological Templates: Fabrication and Potential Applications. *Chem.–Eur. J.* **2002**, *8*, 5481–5485.
4. Lvov, Yu.; Decher, G.; Sukhorukov, G. Assembly of Thin Films by Means of Successive Deposition of Alternate Layers of DNA and Poly(allylamine). *Macromolecules* **1993**, *26*, 5396–5399.
5. Stuart, M. A. C.; Huck, W. T. S.; Genzer, J.; Müller, M.; Ober, C.; Stamm, M.; Sukhorukov, G. B.; Szleifer, I.; Tsukruk, V. V.; Urban, M.; et al. Emerging Applications of Stimuli-responsive Polymer Materials. *Nat. Mater.* **2010**, *9*, 101–113.
6. *Layer-by-Layer Films for Biomedical Applications*; Picart, C., Caruso, F., Voegel J.-C., Eds.; Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA: Weinheim, Germany, 2015.

- 1
2
3 7. Sukhorukov, G. B.; Antipov, A. A.; Voigt, A.; Donath, E.; Möhwald, H. pH-Controlled
4
5 Macromolecule Encapsulation in and Release from Polyelectrolyte Multilayer
6
7 Nanocapsules. *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2001**, *22*, 44–46.
- 8
9
10 8. Caruso, F.; Trau, D.; Möhwald H.; Renneberg R.; Enzyme Encapsulation in Layer-by-
11
12 Layer Engineered Polymer Multilayer Capsules. *Langmuir* **2000**, *16*, 1485–1488.
- 13
14
15 9. Johnston, A. P. R.; Cortez, C.; Angelatos, A. S.; Caruso, F. Layer-by-Layer Engineered
16
17 Capsules and Their Applications. *Curr. Opin. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2006**, *11*, 203–
18
19 209.
- 20
21
22 10. Qiu, X.; Leporatti, S.; Donath, E.; Möhwald, H. Studies on the Drug Release Properties
23
24 of Polysaccharide Multilayers Encapsulated Ibuprofen Microparticles. *Langmuir* **2001**,
25
26 *17*, 5375–5380.
- 27
28
29 11. Qiu, X.; Donath, E.; Möhwald H. Permeability of Ibuprofen in Various Polyelectrolyte
30
31 Multilayers. *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **2001**, *286*, 591–597.
- 32
33
34 12. Mao, Z.; Ma, L.; Gao, C.; Shen, J. Preformed Microcapsules for Loading and Sustained
35
36 Release of Ciprofloxacin Hydrochloride. *J. Controlled Release* **2005**, *104*, 193–202.
- 37
38
39 13. Cheng, Ch.; Yaroshchuk, A.; Bruening, M. L. Fundamentals of Selective Ion Transport
40
41 through Multilayer Polyelectrolyte Membranes. *Langmuir* **2013**, *29*, 1885–1892.
- 42
43
44 14. Miller, M. D.; Bruening, M. L. Correlation of the Swelling and Permeability of
45
46 Polyelectrolyte Multilayer Films. *Chem. Mater.* **2005**, *17*, 5375–5381.
- 47
48
49 15. Liu, X.; Bruening, M. L. Size-Selective Transport of Uncharged Solutes through
50
51 Multilayer Polyelectrolyte Membranes. *Chem. Mater.* **2004**, *16*, 351–357.
- 52
53
54 16. Klitzing R.; Möhwald, H. A Realistic Diffusion Model for Ultrathin Polyelectrolyte
55
56 Films. *Macromolecules* **1996**, *29*, 6901–6906.
- 57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 17. Donath, E.; Vardanyan, I.; Meyer, S.; Murray, R. A.; Moya, S. E.; Navoyan, Z.;
4
5 Arakelyan, V. Atypical Diffusion Monitored by Flow Cytometry: Slow Diffusion of
6
7 Small Molecules in Polyelectrolyte Multilayers. *Nanoscale* **2018**, *10*, 765–772.
8
9
- 10 18. Meyer, S.; Pescador P.; Donath, E. Fluorescence Boost in Polyelectrolyte Multilayer
11
12 Architectures. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2008**, *112*, 1427–1434.
13
- 14 19. Schnäckel, A.; Hiller, S.; Reibetanz, U.; Donath, E. Fluorescent Bead Arrays by Means
15
16 of Layer-By-Layer Polyelectrolyte Adsorption. *Soft Matter* **2007**, *3*, 200–206.
17
18
- 19 20. Ghostine, R. A.; Schlenoff, J. B. Ion Diffusion Coefficients through Polyelectrolyte
20
21 Multilayers: Temperature and Charge Dependence. *Langmuir* **2011**, *27*, 8241–8247.
22
23
- 24 21. Jaber, J. A.; Schlenoff, J. B. Counterions and Water in Polyelectrolyte Multilayers: A
25
26 Tale of Two Polycations. *Langmuir* **2007**, *23*, 896–901.
27
- 28 22. Iturri Ramos, J. J.; Stahl, S.; Richter, R. P.; Moya, S. E. Water Content and Buildup of
29
30 Poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride)/Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate) and
31
32 Poly(allylamine hydrochloride)/Poly(sodium 4-styrenesulfonate) Polyelectrolyte
33
34 Multilayers Studied by an in Situ Combination of a Quartz Crystal Microbalance with
35
36 Dissipation Monitoring and Spectroscopic Ellipsometry. *Macromolecules* **2010**, *43*,
37
38 9063–9070.
39
40
- 41 23. Song, L.; Sun, W.; Gao, J. Time Dependent Chloride Diffusion Coefficient in Concrete.
42
43 *J. Wuhan Univ. Technol. Mater. Sci. Ed.* **2013**, *28*, 314–319.
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